

COGNITIVE APPROACH IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation : Cognitive linguistics views linguistic cognition as indistinguishable from general cognition and thus seeks explanation of linguistic phenomena in terms of general cognitive strategies, such as metaphor and metonymy. In this article, there are given historical background of cognitive linguistics and examples for it.

Keywords: cognitive linguistics, cognitive strategies, metaphor, metonymy, CL.

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive linguistics is the science of human cognition - is recognized as one of the central areas of cognitology. Cognitive term derived from the English word "cognitive" and from Latin and Greek. It is related to the concepts of knowledge, understanding and thinking. Knowledge of the world and reality, perception, reflection in mind and language, communication through language, transmission and reception of information is not a simple phenomenon. Cognitive linguistics in philosophy not limited to the theory of knowledge, but connecting language with thinking and its creation psychological, biological and neurophysiological aspects of social, cultural, makes a deep scientific study of its organic connection with linguistic phenomena. American psychologist H. Gardner at the intersection of cognitive sciences six disciplines (philosophy, psychology, linguistics, anthropology, artificial intelligence, neurology) and the only one scientific goal - accumulation, processing of knowledge in natural and artificial systems. He noted that he would be busy looking for a solution to the problems of its application. (Gardner 1987)¹

The central organizing theme of cognitive linguistics is the idea that language is an integral part of cognition. Thus, linguistic facts ought to be explained in terms of

¹ Safarov Sh. Cognitive linguistics. "Sangzor" publishing house, 2006 - 92 p.

general cognitive mechanisms that psychologists and neurobiologists have previously demonstrated. Language facts are understood via the lens of a usage-based model, which bases language on real-world usage occurrences. Therefore, data represents real language use for a cognitive linguist.

METHODS (Cognition and Language)

Linguistic cognition is an intrinsic aspect of human cognition as a whole, and for a cognitive linguist, it is just cognition. There is nothing unique or distinct about linguistic cognition from other types of cognition. This means that people anticipate language to reflect the patterns of cognition that neurobiologists and psychologists have observed. Moreover, there is no cognitive difference between the different linguistic phenomena. Although discussing different "levels" or "modules" of language is frequently helpful and practical for linguists, cognitive linguists believe that these distinctions are artificial.

The truth is that all of the "parts" of language are in constant communication with one another and aren't actually "parts" at all; rather, they constitute a single, cohesive phenomenon that works in tandem with the more expansive phenomena of cognition and general consciousness. It is a common observation among linguists that boundaries between conventional linguistic phenomena can be breached. For instance, phonology can be influenced by morphology, semantics, syntax, and pragmatics; additionally, it has been demonstrated that syntax is susceptible to the interplay between phonology, semantics, and pragmatics. It may not come as a surprise that these objects are not perfectly distinct, but as cognitive linguists, we anticipate, seek, and emphasize this kind of data rather than dismissing it as trivial or incidental.

The goal of linguistics is to be an exact science. In our society, precision and science are highly respected and held in high regard for their authority. A scientific conclusion can only be considered operationally defined if it can be demonstrated to be repeatable, or predictable. But as Croft has shown, variation is one of the best-documented phenomena we are aware of; if linguistic events were genuinely

predictable, there wouldn't be any.² There is ample evidence from historical linguistics and dialectology that you may achieve an astounding range of outcomes even when you start from roughly the same linguistic starting point. Therefore, cognitive linguistics is mainly the cause and effect of human linguistic activity is a research, "explanatory" field of science.³

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Metaphor

A mapping from one domain to another is called a metaphor. In other words, if a person takes an idea that has been established in one domain and tries to implement it in another, a metaphor has occurred. The human body in physical space is the domain in which most human knowledge is created and is also the source domain for metaphor. Emotions, states of being, and time are common target domains. Three fundamental categories of metaphor are identified by Lakoff and Johnson as orientational, ontological, and structural.⁴

For instance, to go through a lot in life, to be without direction in life, to be a crossroads in one's life.

Metonymy

When one thing, the "source," substitutes for another, the "target," metonymy is present. Metonymies can therefore be represented as formulas for SOURCE FOR TARGET. For example,

Alisher Navai takes up a whole shelf in my library.

There is used an AGENT FOR PRODUCT metonymy, where the agent, Alisher Navai, stands in for his products, i.e. books he has authored.

² Clausner, T., & Croft, W. Domains and Image Schemas. *Cognitive Linguistics*, 1999, 31 p.

³ Peter Robinson and Nick C. Ellis. *Handbook of cognitive linguistics and second language acquisition: Handbook*. – Taylor & Francis e-Library, 2008. – 566 p.

⁴ George Lakoff and Mark Johnson. *Metaphors we live by: Language, thought and culture*, 2003, 21 p.

Most work on metonymy has thus far focused on lexical metonymy (such as the examples above), and there are roughly three main strategies for classifying metonymy, involving contiguity, frames, and domains.

CONCLUSION

Knowledge of the language system as the main goal of cognitive linguistics determination of participation and share in the process is determined. Language units the participation of acquired knowledge in linguistic realization and linguistic activity determining the role of cognitive analysis in the formation and "processing" of information one of the views. A cognitivist is a linguist who thinks of linguistic phenomena He is interested in his role in his work, his duties. But this interest is simple it's not. He (cognitivist) is the emergence of relations between linguistic and thinking activities looks for the leading causes, and the communication texts that are the result of these causes - tries to understand and analyze linguistic structures from their content and content.

References:

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